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Simulating Soot Formation in Model Flames

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Abstract: We are interested in the simulation of wildland fires at the landscape level, including the formation of soot and other particulates. Emissions of soot from wildland fires pose significant problems for human health, air quality, and regional and global climate. Furthermore, in recent years these problems have increased in severity with the advent of mega-fires that can last almost an entire fire season. Here we focus on the behavior of a kinetic mechanism that uses a sectional approach to model soot and compare simulations with experimental data from a model flame for which there are temperature and soot volume fraction experimental data. Both Cantera and OpenSmoke++ Suite were used, and results from, and ease of use of, the two codes are compared. Finally, we briefly discuss issues associated with mechanism reduction, which will be required to develop a useful mechanism for large numerical simulations.

Keywords: *Soot, Model Flames, Soot Modeling,*

1. Introduction

We are currently interested in modeling wildland fires at the landscape level, including the production of major pollutants. Here we report on the first step toward the development of a soot modeling approach suitable for use in landscape-scale large-eddy simulation (LES) calculations.

Wildland fires have large environmental and economic costs. According to the National Interagency Fire Center (NIFC), between 2010 and 2015 wildland fires consumed over 29 million acres of timber, grass, and brush in the U.S., the equivalent of nearly half the surface area of Colorado. Over the same period, \$8 billion was spent on fire suppression by federal agencies and almost 11 million additional acres of wildland fuel were removed through preventative prescribed burns. Nearly two thousand structures were lost as the result of wildland fires in 2014 alone. In 2018 three of the largest fires in California history burned: Mendocino Complex (459,123 acres), Carr (229,651 acres), and Camp (153,336 acres). It is likely that climate change will contribute to increased wildland-fire activity, particularly in the Western U.S.[1].

In addition to the obvious environmental effects and costs of suppression and property damage associated with wildfires, there are significant secondary health effects and costs [2–4]. Wildfire smoke contains fine and coarse particulate matter (PM), and gases, such as carbon monoxide (CO), methane, nitrous oxide (N₂O), nitrogen oxides (NO_x), volatile organic compounds (VOC), and

many other air toxics [5]. Emissions also contain a number of trace metals. Air quality is further affected by the formation of secondary pollutants, such as organic aerosols, and ozone generated by the photoreaction of NO_x and VOCs in the atmosphere [6].

In Glusman et al. [7] we reported on the reduction of a large reaction mechanism (137 species/4533 reactions) that was developed by the CRECK Modeling Group specifically to use with their biomass pyrolysis mechanism. We presented several skeletal mechanisms, each with different error levels. They ranged from 71 species/1179 reactions at 1% error, to 54 species/204 reactions with average maximum error of 24%.

Modeling soot production requires a starting mechanism that includes species as large as polycyclic aromatic hydrocarbons (PAHs) with several rings, saturated and unsaturated aliphatics, oxygenated aliphatics and aromatics, and free-radical counterparts of some of these species. In addition, one must include a soot-formation model. Two approaches to modeling particulates have been used in conventional CFD simulations: sectional and moment. Chemical Discrete Sectional Model (CDSM) methods divide particles into pseudo-species or BINs, and kinetic rate equations are added to the base mechanism for each size bin. One must then provide source and sink terms for each bin. Moment methods involve writing kinetic rate equations for moments of a particle size or volume distribution.

When attempting to develop a kinetic reaction mechanism, one must have some "truth" against which to measure success. Hopefully the "truth" is based on firm experimental or theoretical foundations. However, when reducing a preexisting mechanism, "truth" is often taken as the original mechanism. In this work, we examine whether the CRECK soot mechanism can reasonably reproduce experimental data generated by Campbell et al. [8]. We also compare the efficiency of two open source chemical kinetic codes.

2. Methods

2.1 Soot Mechanism

The soot mechanism we are using is that developed by the CRECK Modeling Group as reported by Saggese et al.[9] and Pejpichestakul et al.[10] The gas-phase high-temperature CRECK mechanism (244 species and ~ 6000 reactions) is based on a C₀–C₃ core mechanism developed using the H₂/O₂ and C₁/C₂ subsets from Metcalfe et al. [11], C₃ from Burke et al.[12], and heavier fuels from Ranzi et al. [13]. The thermochemical properties were obtained, when available, from the ATcT database of Ruscic [14] or from Burcat's database [15]. Properties for some species were obtained using the group additivity method [16]. The kinetic mechanism with thermodynamic and transport properties can be found on the CRECK website [17].

In developing the soot portion of the mechanism, the HACA mechanism described by Frenklach was revised based on the recent theoretical study of Mebel et al.[18]. To control the overall size of the mechanism, where appropriate, many isomer species were lumped. The relative branching ratios were taken into account in the lumped mechanism, treating reactions with explicit forward and backward rates. The final mechanism involves 20 lumped species and 16 radicals for the progressive growth from naphthalene to C₂₀ species, which are considered the first soot precursors. Mass growth through light and heavy resonantly stabilized radicals (from propargyl C₃H₃, up to indenyl (C₉H₇)) is also included [13].

The soot mechanism, based on a discrete sectional model, is then coupled to the PAH sub-

mechanism to describe the evolution from gas phase to solid particles. The entire range of carbon atoms comprising heavy PAH and soot particles (from 20 up to more than 10^8 C atoms) is divided into 25 bins of lumped-pseudo species. The bin-to-bin mass ratio is a factor of two as recommended by Hounslow et al. [19]. Each bin contains three different hydrogenation levels, i.e., hydrogen-to-carbon (H/C) atomic ratios, denoted "A", "B", and "C", varying from 0.8 for BIN1A to 0.05 for BIN25C. The first four BINs (up to 160 carbon atoms) are heavy PAHs, while heavier BINs are soot primary particles (up to 4×10^4 carbon atoms) and soot aggregates. Thus, the soot kinetic model involves 150 molecular and radical species for describing the formation of soot particles up to $\sim 0.2 \mu\text{m}$, i.e. 3.2×10^8 carbon atoms.

The source and sink terms for the kinetic equations consist of surface growth, nucleation, coagulation, and oxidation processes. The surface-growth reactions include the HACA mechanism and PAH and other gaseous-species-condensation reactions. The condensing species are aromatic molecules and radicals starting from benzene and phenyl radical. The complete soot sub-mechanism consists of ~ 400 species and $\sim 25,000$ reactions. Further details on the soot model are available in [9, 10].

2.2 Experimental Data

The experimental data used for comparison are taken from a surface stabilized flat flame described by Campbell et al.[8, 20]. The burner measures 38.1 mm inner diameter with a surrounding shroud with a 50.8 mm outer diameter. The stabilization plate is the same diameter as the burner, 38.1 mm, and is positioned 13.6 mm above the burner surface. One-dimensional coherent anti-Stokes Raman spectroscopy (CARS) imaging was used to extract high-fidelity flame temperatures along the centerline of the burner [21]. Laser-induced incandescence (LII) was used to measure soot-volume fractions.

The data used are from the flame labeled ME1. For this flame, the flows are C_2H_4 673 sccm, O_2 961 sccm and N_2 3616 sccm, for an equivalence ratio of 2.1. There is a shroud flow of nitrogen. The inlet temperature is held at 300 K, and the stagnation surface temperature at 375 K.

2.3 Comparing LII Measurements to Sectional Simulation Data

A somewhat complex question involves trying to relate experimental results obtained by various measurement techniques to sectional concentration results. The Pejpichestakul et al.[10] mechanism we are using provides output for the mole and mass fractions of twenty-five size classes, each with three closed shell species of different H/C ratios, along with corresponding surface species. The data we are using were obtained by the laser-induced incandescence method (LII). As discussed by Michelsen [22], LII has become the most commonly used technique for soot distribution and volume-fraction measurements of fully mature and nearly mature or partially graphitized soot in combustors. Detection by LII requires that the particles absorb strongly at the laser wavelength and are refractory, i.e., sufficiently mature and graphitic to be able to be heated to temperatures above ~ 3500 K without vaporizing or undergoing photolysis. Incipient particles generally do not produce LII signal. Therefore, to directly compare numerical and experimental results requires making assumptions about which particles contribute to the LII results. It also requires relating the concentration of those particles to the volume fraction.

2.4 Simulation Software

Two kinetic codes were used to simulate the flame discussed above. Cantera and OpenSmooke++ Suite.

2.4.1 Cantera

Cantera [23] is an open-source suite of tools for problems involving chemical kinetics, thermodynamics, and transport processes. Cantera was originally developed by Prof. David G. Goodwin at the California Institute of Technology. Cantera is a fast, relatively easy to use code, now in common use throughout the combustion community. However, it is limited to fairly simple problems of zero or one dimension. Cantera automates chemical kinetic, thermodynamic, and transport calculations so that the users can efficiently incorporate detailed chemical thermo-kinetics and transport models into their calculations. Cantera is currently used for many applications, including combustion, detonations, electrochemical energy conversion and storage, fuel cells, batteries, aqueous electrolyte solutions, plasmas, and thin film deposition. In this study we ran Cantera using the Python script `stagnation_flame.py`. Cantera has a gas-radiation model, the effectiveness of which we explore in the Results section.

2.4.2 OpenSMOKE++

OpenSMOKE++[17] is a general framework developed by the CRECK Modeling Group for numerical simulations of reacting systems with detailed kinetic mechanisms, including thousands of chemical species and reactions [24–26]. The advantage of the OpenSMOKE++ Suite programming system is that many of the functions can be incorporated into large OpenFOAM CFD simulations, and OpenFOAM is the platform that we use for wildfire simulations.

OpenSMOKE++ Suite can handle simulations of ideal reactors, shock-tubes, rapid compression machines, 1D laminar flames, and multidimensional reacting systems, and it provides useful numerical tools, such as sensitivity and rate of production analyses. In this study, the surface stabilized flat flame was simulated using the opposed jet diffusion flame solver in OpenSMOKE++ Suite, modified to replace the oxidizer stream by a wall.

OpenSMOKE++ Suite contains both gas and particle radiation models. In the results we provide a comparison between solutions with and without radiation. OpenSMOKE++ Suite also provides a soot deposition module, which we included in our simulations.

3. Results and Discussion

3.1 Temperature Distribution

Fig. 1 shows a comparison between the simulated and measured temperature profiles. The Cantera line without radiation most closely approaches the experimental data. Including gas-phase radiation lowers the temperature at the peak by about 30K. The OpenSMOKE++ simulation without soot radiation is close to, but not exactly the same, as the Cantera with radiation result, and the OpenSMOKE++ simulation with soot radiation results in a lower temperature by about 60 K. With the exception of the OpenSMOKE++ simulation with soot radiation, the other three lines fall within the uncertainty bars for the measured values.

Figure 1: Comparison of Simulated and Measured Temperature Profile

3.2 Soot Volume Fraction

As discussed above, calculating soot volume fraction requires an assumption of which simulated particle types to use. Since the LII method mainly probes mature soot with small H/C ratios, we have chosen to select only the C-type particles, those having an H/C ratio of 0.05. Based on the discussion by Michelsen [22], we chose to select all C-type particles with diameter larger than 2 nm (BIN5-25,C).

Two approaches were used to estimate the soot volume fraction. The first, based on the mass fraction of C-type particles was calculated using the following equation

$$V_f = \sum_i y_i \frac{\rho}{\rho_{soot}} \quad (1)$$

where V_f is the volume fraction, y_i the mass fraction of the i -th C type particle, ρ the local gas density, and ρ_{soot} the soot bulk density. Because LII probes mature soot, the appropriate value of density to use is something close to that of graphite. From Michelsen [27], we use the following formula to calculate soot density:

$$\rho_{soot} = W / (VM * (1 + \alpha * (T - 298.15))^3) \quad (2)$$

Here W is the average molecular weight of the soot particle, 11.49 gm/mol for a carbon-to-hydrogen ratio of 20, VM is a parameter equal to 5.91 cm³/mol, and α is a parameter equal to $2.163 \times 10^{-5} \text{ K}^{-1}$.

The second method involves calculating the volumes of each particle based on the diameter given in Pejpichestakul et al. [10], weighted by the mole fraction times the local number density.

$$V_f = \sum_i \frac{4}{3} \pi \left(\frac{d_i}{2} \right)^3 \times x_i n_{tot} \quad (3)$$

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where d_i is the primary-particle diameter, x_i , the mole fraction, and n_{tot} , the primary-particle number density. A comparison between the two methods using the OpenSMOKE++ output is shown in Fig. 2.

Figure 2: Comparison of Mass Fraction and Volume Method for Calculating Volume Fraction

Fig.3 shows a comparison between the calculated soot volume fractions and the data from Campbell et al. [8]. The error bars on the experimental data line reflect an estimated uncertainty of $\pm 17\%$. This comparison indicates that Pejpichestakul et al. [10] over predicts the amount of soot produced in this flame.

One difference between the Cantera and OpenSMOKE++ simulations is the inclusion of a soot deposition model in OpenSMOKE++, and the shapes of the curves reflect this difference. In the experiment, soot is deposited on the stagnation plate. The result is a depression of the soot profile as the stagnation plate is approached. Another difference is that Cantera does not have a soot radiation module.

4. Discussion

The results presented represent an attempt to simulate one flame geometry and operating condition. There are numerous approximations involved in reducing the experimental LII data and building the soot reaction mechanism and then converting soot concentrations into volume fractions. These approximations can introduce considerable differences between the data and simulations. The mechanism was developed by comparison with numerous other data sets, and each of these data sets have their own uncertainty. Nonetheless, the temperature predictions are almost entirely within the uncertainty bars, and the volume fractions within an order of magnitude. Furthermore, given that the mechanism over predicts the soot concentrations, were the mechanism adjusted to match

Figure 3: Comparison of Mass Fraction Method and Data from [8]

the volume-fraction data, the model with soot radiation included might provide a temperature profile that gives better agreement with the measured temperature values.

While we started out using Cantera because of its simplicity of use, it became clear that OpenSMOKE++ is better suited for our future use due to it being designed specifically for modeling combustion with soot, and its expand-ability to multi-dimensional geometries and inclusion in OpenFoam CFD. The ability to model both gas phase and soot radiation, and include soot transport and deposition, are both important features.

The CRECK soot mechanism is currently too large to be useful in a larger scale CFD simulation. However, we have previously reduced the CRECK detailed gas-phase combustion mechanism bio1412 that was designed to use with their biomass pyrolysis model [7]. That mechanism was reduced using the Model Automatic Reduction Software (MARS) package [28–31]. The reduction employs the directed relation graph with error propagation (DRGEP) and sensitivity analysis (SA) method, followed by reaction elimination, which Niemeyer and colleagues have shown to be effective for reducing various surrogate fuel models. We are currently working to perform a similar reduction with the soot mechanism.

5. Conclusions

Simulations using both Cantera and OpenSMOKE++ Suite and using the Pejpichestakul et al.[10] soot mechanism were carried out and compared with temperature and soot volume fraction data from the ME1 flame of Campbell et al.[8]. The results are encouraging, given the uncertainty in both the experimental data and the mechanism. Future work will involve reducing the mechanism to the point where a skeletal mechanism can be run in a landscape scale LES simulation.

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References

- [1] A. L. Westerling, H. G. Hidalgo, D. R. Cayan, and T. W. Swetnam, Warming and Earlier Spring Increase Western U.S. Forest Wildfire Activity, *Science* 313 (2006) 940–943.
- [2] W. E. Cascio, Wildland fire smoke and human health, *Science of the Total Environment*, The 624 (2018) 586–595.
- [3] J. C. Liu, G. Pereira, S. A. Uhl, M. A. Bravo, and M. L. Bell, A systematic review of the physical health impacts from non-occupational exposure to wildfire smoke, *Environmental Research* 136 (2015) 120–132.
- [4] L. A. Richardson, P. A. Champ, and J. B. Loomis, The hidden cost of wildfires: Economic valuation of health effects of wildfire smoke exposure in Southern California, *Journal of Forest Economics* 18 (2012) 14–35.
- [5] S. P. Urbanski, W. M. Hao, and S. Baker, Chapter 4 Chemical Composition of Wildland Fire Emissions, in: *Wildland Fires and Air Pollution*, Elsevier, 2008, pp. 79–107.
- [6] D. A. Jaffe and N. L. Wigder, Ozone production from wildfires: A critical review, *Atmospheric Environment* 51 (2012) 1–10.
- [7] J. F. Glusman, K. E. Niemeyer, A. S. Makowiecki, N. T. Wimer, C. Lapointe, G. B. Rieker, P. E. Hamlington, and J. W. Daily, Reduced Gas-Phase Kinetic Models for Burning of Douglas Fir, *Frontiers in Mechanical Engineering* 5 (2019) 892–8.
- [8] M. F. Campbell, P. E. Schrader, A. L. Catalano, K. O. Johansson, G. A. Bohlin, N. K. Richards-Henderson, C. J. Kliewer, and H. A. Michelsen, A small porous-plug burner for studies of combustion chemistry and soot formation, *Review of Scientific Instruments* 88 (2017) 125106–11.
- [9] C. Saggese, S. Ferrario, J. Camacho, A. Cuoci, A. Frassoldati, E. Ranzi, H. Wang, and T. Faravelli, Kinetic modeling of particle size distribution of soot in a premixed burner-stabilized stagnation ethylene flame, *COMBUSTION AND FLAME* 162 (2015) 3356–3369.
- [10] W. Pejpichestakul, E. Ranzi, M. Pelucchi, A. Frassoldati, A. Cuoci, A. Parente, and T. Faravelli, Examination of a soot model in premixed laminar flames at fuel-rich conditions, *Proceedings Of The Combustion Institute* 37 (2019) 1013–1021.
- [11] W. K. Metcalfe, S. M. Burke, S. S. Ahmed, and H. J. Curran, A Hierarchical and Comparative Kinetic Modeling Study of C₁C₂Hydrocarbon and Oxygenated Fuels, *International Journal Of Chemical Kinetics* 45 (2013) 638–675.

- [12] S. M. Burke, U. Burke, R. M. Donagh, O. Mathieu, I. Osorio, C. Keesee, A. Morones, E. L. Petersen, W. Wang, T. A. DeVerter, M. A. Oehlschlaeger, B. Rhodes, R. K. Hanson, D. F. Davidson, B. W. Weber, C.-J. Sung, J. Santner, Y. Ju, F. M. Haas, F. L. Dryer, E. N. Volkov, E. J. K. Nilsson, A. A. Konnov, M. Alrefae, F. Khaled, A. Farooq, P. Dirrenberger, P.-A. Glaude, F. Battin-Leclerc, and H. J. Curran, An experimental and modeling study of propene oxidation. Part 2: Ignition delay time and flame speed measurements, *COMBUSTION AND FLAME* 162 (2015) 296–314.
- [13] E. Ranzi, A. Frassoldati, R. Grana, A. Cuoci, T. Faravelli, A. P. Kelley, and C. K. Law, Hierarchical and comparative kinetic modeling of laminar flame speeds of hydrocarbon and oxygenated fuels, *Progress In Energy And Combustion Science* 38 (2012) 468–501.
- [14] B. Ruscic, Active Thermochemical Tables: Sequential Bond Dissociation Enthalpies of Methane, Ethane, and Methanol and the Related Thermochemistry, *The Journal of Physical Chemistry A* 119 (2015) 7810–7837.
- [15] E. Goos, A. Burcat, and B. Ruscic, *Extended Third Millenium Ideal Gas Thermochemical Database with updates from Active Thermochemical Tables*, <http://burcat.technion.ac.il/dir>, 2017.
- [16] S. W. Benson, F. R. Cruickshank, D. M. GOLDEN, G. R. Haugen, H. E. O’Neal, A. S. Rodgers, R. Shaw, and R. Walsh, Additivity rules for the estimation of thermochemical properties, *Chemical Reviews* 69 (1969) 279–324.
- [17] A. Cuoci, A. Frassoldati, T. Faravelli, E. Ranzi, and A. Stgni, *OpenSMOKE*, <https://www.opensmokepp.polimi.it>, 2019.
- [18] A. M. Mebel, Y. Georgievskii, A. W. Jasper, and S. J. Klippenstein, Temperature- and pressure-dependent rate coefficients for the HACA pathways from benzene to naphthalene, *Proceedings Of The Combustion Institute* 36 (2017) 919–926.
- [19] M. Hounslow, R. Ryall, and V. Marshall, A Discretized Population Balance Equation for Nucleation, Growth and Aggregation, *AIChE Journal* 34 (1988) 18211832.
- [20] M. F. Campbell, G. A. Bohlin, P. E. Schrader, R. P. Bambha, C. J. Kliwer, K. O. Johansson, and H. A. Michelsen, Design and characterization of a linear Hencken-type burner, *Review of Scientific Instruments* 87 (2016) 115114–13.
- [21] A. Bohlin and C. J. Kliwer, Direct Coherent Raman Temperature Imaging and Wideband Chemical Detection in a Hydrocarbon Flat Flame, *The Journal of Physical Chemistry Letters* 6 (2015) 643–649.
- [22] H. A. Michelsen, Probing soot formation, chemical and physical evolution, and oxidation: A review of in situ diagnostic techniques and needs, *Proceedings Of The Combustion Institute* 36 (2017) 717–735.
- [23] D. G. Goodwin, R. L. Speth, H. K. Moffat, and B. W. Weber, *Cantera: An Object-oriented Software Toolkit for Chemical Kinetics, Thermodynamics, and Transport Processes*, <https://www.cantera.org>, Version 2.4.0, 2018, DOI: 10.5281/zenodo.1174508.
- [24] A. Cuoci, A. Frassoldati, T. Faravelli, and E. Ranzi, OpenSMOKE++: An object-oriented framework for the numerical modeling of reactive systems with detailed kinetic mechanisms, *Computer Physics Communications* 192 (2015) 237–264.

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- [25] A. Cuoci, A. Frassoldati, T. Faravelli, and E. Ranzi, Numerical Modeling of Laminar Flames with Detailed Kinetics Based on the Operator-Splitting Method, *Energy & Fuels* 27 (2013) 7730–7753.
- [26] A. Stagni, A. Cuoci, A. Frassoldati, T. Faravelli, and E. Ranzi, Lumping and Reduction of Detailed Kinetic Schemes: an Effective Coupling, *Ind. Eng. Chem. Res* 53 (2014) 9004–9016.
- [27] H. A. Michelsen, Effects of Maturity and Temperature on Soot Density and Specific Heat, In Preparation (2019).
- [28] K. E. Niemeyer, C.-J. Sung, and M. P. Raju, Skeletal mechanism generation for surrogate fuels using directed relation graph with error propagation and sensitivity analysis, *Combustion and Flame* 157 (2010) 1760–1770.
- [29] K. E. Niemeyer and C.-J. Sung, On the importance of graph search algorithms for DRGEP-based mechanism reduction methods, *Combustion and Flame* 158 (2011) 1439–1443.
- [30] K. E. Niemeyer and C.-J. Sung, Mechanism reduction for multicomponent surrogates: A case study using toluene reference fuels, *Combustion and Flame* 161 (2014) 2752–2764.
- [31] K. E. Niemeyer and C.-J. Sung, Reduced chemistry for a gasoline surrogate valid at engine-relevant conditions, *Energy & Fuels* 29 (2015) 1172–1185.